

Book of Abstracts

First Annual International Conference on Religion, Culture, and Peace

Rey Ty

Editor-in-Chief

Department of Peace Studies (DPS)

Religion, Culture, and Peace Laboratory (RCP Lab)

Faculty of Humanities and Communications

Payap University

In Cooperation with

The Mennonite Central Committee

Chiang Mai, Thailand

April 28-29, 2022

COMPENDIUM

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Number	1
Profile	
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Title	
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Sex	Female
Abstract Proposal 1	
Title	Inclusive-Dialogic Christian Education in the Context of Religious Diversity in Indonesia
Problem Statement	How is the influence of religious education in the phenomenon of the increasing trend of religious intolerance in universities in Indonesia?
Research Purpose or Questions	How is the influence of Christian religious education provided in Christian Universities on the reduction and prevention of religious intolerance among the students?
Literature or Theory	Christian education approach from Mai-Anh Le Tran, namely Communicability, Redeemability and Educability in responding to the phenomenon of religious intolerance tendencies in universities in Indonesia.
Research Methods	This study uses a practical theological framework developed by Robert R. Osmer and Christian education approach from Mai-Anh Le Tran
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	Christian Education Approach that develops Communicability, Redeemability and Educability becomes an alternative model of inclusive religious education in an effort to develop peace and religious tolerance in the context of Indonesia's religious diversity.
Conclusion or recommendations	An Alternative Model of Inclusive Religious Education in the Pluralistic Indonesian Context
Key Word 1	Religious Education
Key Word 2	Christian Religious Education
Key Word 3	Christian Education Approach from Tran
Key Word 4	Practical Theological Framework from R Osmer
Key Word 5	Inclusive Religious Education

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	2
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Abstract Proposal 2	
Title	TAU SŪG AS ETHNO-TOPONYMIC IDENTITY
Problem Statement	This paper addresses the problem of misunderstanding, misrecognition and misnomer about the origin of the word “Tau Sug” versus “Suluk” that are claimed to be different identities of one of the coastal ethnic groups in Sabah and Sulu archipelago with regards to the context of modern nation-states of Malaysia and the Philippines.
Research Purpose or Questions	The purpose of this paper is to explain and correct the conflicting narratives, the etymology and origin of these words.
Literature or Theory	This paper explores the etymology of the “Tau Sug” and “Suluk” identities using toponymic theory.
Research Methods	Qualitative data are going to be collected and analyzed from previous writings and literature.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	The expected findings of this paper are to show that the origin and etymology of this identity was based on a self-reference, endonymic and exonymic.
Conclusion or recommendations	This paper expects to conclude that as far as history, socio-cultural, geographical, statehood, toponymic, maritime, sea, and linguistic context is concerned, the Tau Sug as an ethnic group, may they be called Suluk, they are indigenous to the region that is currently composed of different nation-states in insular Southeast Asia. And hopes to recommend for the future writing to not differentiate this identity as their roots are the same.
Key Word 1	Tau Sūg
Key Word 2	Suluk
Key Word 3	Misnomer
Key Word 4	Sulu Archipelago
Key Word 5	Sabah

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	3
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Title	
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Country	United States of America
Sex	Male
Abstract Proposal 3	
Title	Aristotle, Gautama Buddha, & Jesus Christ: Virtue Ethics as a Cohesive Framework for Interreligious Dialogue and Ethical Deliberation Among Civil Engineering Students in Myanmar
Problem Statement	Societies are not well-served if engineers have not learned to engage in ethical deliberation and navigate competing religious/philosophical viewpoints, yet ethics courses have seldom been taught in Myanmar.
Research Purpose or Questions	The author is presently conducting research to develop a contextually appropriate engineering ethics course that considers how various religious views influence ethical deliberation and interreligious dialogue among engineering students in Myanmar.
Literature or Theory	The Noble Eightfold Path, The Dhammapada, Aristotle's Nicomachean Ethics, the Christian Bible, MacIntyre's "A Short History of Ethics: A History of Moral Philosophy from the Homeric Age to the 20th Century", etc.
Research Methods	The author utilizes an empirical method to analyze primary sources such as interviews with students and religious leaders in Myanmar, as well as secondary sources such as peer-reviewed journal articles and other academic and religious literature.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	Aristotelian Virtue Ethics has been identified as the most appropriate framework of emphasis for this course, given that both Theravada Buddhism and Christianity share significant commonalities with virtue ethics.
Conclusion or recommendations	Inclusion of ethics courses, with particular emphasis on the framework of virtue ethics, will prove advantageous in terms of providing opportunities for students to engage in constructive interreligious dialogue and explore how various religions and philosophies inform various virtues that are relevant to the practice of engineering and everyday life.
Key Word 1	engineering ethics
Key Word 2	Burma/Myanmar
Key Word 3	virtue
Key Word 4	interreligious dialogue
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	4
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Title	
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Country	Nigerian
Sex	Female
Abstract Proposal 4	
Title	Women Empowerment and Socio-Economic Development in Northern Nigeria
Problem Statement	Women in northern Nigerian have been neglected from socio-economic activities as a result of lack of adequate education, financial empowerment and cultural barriers.
Research Purpose or Questions	The problems associated with women empowerment and socio-economic development in northern Nigerian.
Literature or Theory	Feminist theory
Research Methods	The content analysis methods where relevant literature addressing women empowerment and socio-economic development in northern Nigerian will be utilized.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	Tackling women empowerment through literacy educating them with skills, abolishing cultural norms and barriers hinged on cultures and religious considerations.
Conclusion or recommendation	The final paper will provide recommendations.
Key Word 1	Women
Key Word 2	Empowerment
Key Word 3	Socio-Economic
Key Word 4	Development
Key Word 5	Northern Nigeria

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	5
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Title	Prof.
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Country	Poland
Sex	Female
Abstract Proposal 5	
Title	Drawing on Fear and Stereotypes to Win Hearts and Minds: The Development of Anti-Muslim Attitudes in Election Campaigns in Poland
Problem Statement	This paper addresses the problem that drawing on fear and stereotypes, Law and Justice (PiS) developed anti-Muslim attitudes in election campaigns in Poland to win elections.
Research Purpose or Questions	The paper aims to explain how the right-wing ruling elites used anti-Muslim and anti-Islam sentiment to increase the level of its support and win votes during elections.
Literature or Theory	This conjecture draws on the assumption that the discursive construction of neo-militant democracy allowed PiS to build their image as the protectors of democracy who safeguard Poland from the external threat.
Research Methods	The research uses the qualitative document analysis of texts distributed by TVP in the period from 2015 to 2019.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	PiS drew upon a belief that Muslims would harm Poland culturally and underlined the cultural differences that would make assimilation of Muslims in Catholic Poland impossible. The party pointed to the incompatibility of Islam and Christianity and claimed that their co-existence may negatively impact the Polish national identity whose part is Christianity.
Conclusion or recommendation	PiS used the strategy of neo-militant democracy to argue that they needed to protect democracy from external enemies and win elections.
Key Word 1	anti-Muslim sentiment
Key Word 2	Poland
Key Word 3	religion and democracy
Key Word 4	election campaign
Key Word 5	Islam

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	6
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Title	Prof.
Name of Institution	ICAES and National San Luis University
Country	Argentina
Sex	Male
Abstract Proposal 6	
Title	Communication, Disinformation, Internet and Development
Problem Statement	This work seeks to relate problematic aspects of today's society such as global warming, deforestation, the increase in the world population, fuel consumption, diseases and viruses, the climate crisis, in the midst of a culture of hyperconsumption and the catastrophe of public health
Research Purpose or Questions	What can academics or citizens of the world do against this?
Literature or Theory	<p>This paper is qualitative and uses library search for document analysis.</p> <p>Anaf, J., Baum, F.E., Fisher, M. et al. (2017). Assessing the health impact of transnational corporations: a case study on McDonald's Australia. <i>Global Health</i> 13, 7. https://doi.org/10.1186/s12992-016-0230-4</p> <p>Bauman, Z. (2007). <i>Vida de consumo</i>. Buenos Aires: FCE.</p> <p>Beyer, R.; Manica, M.; Mora, C. (2021). Shifts in global bat diversity suggest a possible role of climate change in the emergence of SARS-CoV-1 and SARS-CoV-2, <i>Science of The Total Environment</i>, Volume 767, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.145413</p> <p>Cowie, R. ; Bouchet, P. ; and Fontaine, B. (2022). The Sixth Mass Extinction: fact, fiction or speculation? <i>Biol. Rev. Cambridge Philosophical Society</i>. pp. 000–000. 1 doi: 10.1111/brv.12816</p> <p>Lipovetsky, G. y Charles, S. (2006). <i>Les temps hypermodernes</i>. Paris: Lgf</p> <p>McCarthy, J. (2004). <i>What is artificial Intelligence?</i> Stanford University.</p> <p>Peñaloza Acosta, Mónica, Arévalo Cohén, Freddy, & Daza Suárez, Roberto. (2009). Impacto de la gestión tecnológica en el medio ambiente <i>Impact of Technological Management on the Environment</i>. <i>Revista de Ciencias Sociales</i>, 15(2), 306-316. Recuperado en 22 de enero de 2022, de http://ve.scielo.org/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1315-95182009000200010&lng=es&tlng=es.</p> <p>Quiroya, S (2020). <i>Psicopolítica, enjambre, mediatización y comunicación digital en Byung Chul Han</i>. Una crítica inicial. In <i>ReVID</i>, N° 3, pages 60-78.</p>

	<p>https://www.evirtual.unsl.edu.ar/revistas/index.php/revid/article/view/103/76</p> <p>Quiroga, S. (2021). Communication, Public Policies and Environment. International Journal of Global Science Research ISSN: 2348-8344 (Online) Vol. 8, Issue. 2, Abril. Pages. 1499-1507.</p> <p>http://www.ijgsr.com/webadmin/uploads/10.26540ijgsr.v8.i1.2021.175.pdf [DOI: 10.26540/ijgsr.v8.i1.2021.175]</p> <p>The Public Service Media and Public Service Internet Manifesto. (https://ia601407.us.archive.org/31/items/psmi_20220127/psmi.pdf).</p>
Research Methods	Description and analysis of problems and concerns
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	Research in progress - Today we are witnessing a generation that perceives uncertainty scared by the future. The warnings of the scientific community have been ignored in the last fifty years, to take real actions, while world governments look the other way.
Conclusion or recommendations	It is time to become aware of the risks involved in the climate crisis, the technological challenges and risks where governments must fundamentally assume an active attitude and citizens must demand and ensure the progressive transformations that societies need.
Key Word 1	Communication
Key Word 2	dis-information
Key Word 3	Internet
Key Word 4	Development
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

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Title	
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Sex	
Abstract Proposal 7	
Title	Impact of Institutionalised Religion on the Galo Tribe of Arunachal Pradesh, India
Problem Statement	There is not enough research on the the crisis that is taking place in Galo society in reference to thier faith.
Research Purpose or Questions	To study the institutionalisation of tribal religion.
Literature or Theory	This paper uses the theory of animistic belief
Research Methods	Ethnographic study is the research method.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	In order to preserve the true form of indigenous faith, the Galos have started a very similar ways of lifestyle of institutionalised religious organisations.
Conclusion or recommendations	Youth participation is the only way to preserve.
Key Word 1	Donyi polo
Key Word 2	Galos
Key Word 3	
Key Word 4	
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	8
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Country	United States
Sex	Female
Abstract Proposal 8	
Title	Internalization of Higher Education: Community's Involvement in Recruiting International Students
Problem Statement	International students not only bring income to the U.S., but their diverse nature tremendously contributes to the cultural, academic values of the universities. Internationalization of education in the U.S. promotes international goodwill, peace, understanding, and mutual learning. However, the communities are not always included to recruiting international students.
Research Purpose or Questions	The purpose of this study was to examine how the local DeKalb community supports international students in their integration to a new environment and how it impacts the increase of this population of students at Northern Illinois University (NIU).
Literature or Theory	Transnational theory is employed in this paper.
Research Methods	Ethnographic research that included field observations and conversations was designed, and in this scope, it was important to enter a social setting, participate and observe each event. (Emerson et al., 2011).
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	The data obtained found the significance of the role of community support in the example of Network of Nations (NofN) in the international students' integration into the new academic environment. It was also found that NofN collaborates with NIU in recruiting students, but not in other activities. By their active involvement in international student recruitment and hosting, the NofN promotes international peace at the community level where the university is located.
Conclusion or recommendations	The findings might provide in-depth information for higher education administrators to consider the importance of community involvement in recruiting international students and social support in regard to international students' adjustment to new environments.
Key Word 1	internationalization
Key Word 2	higher education
Key Word 3	student recruitment
Key Word 4	community social support
Key Word 5	International goodwill, peace and understanding

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	9
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Sex	
Abstract Proposal 9	
Title	Mother Tongue-based Multilingual Education: A Vehicle for Building Myanmar into Equal and Fair Federal Democratic Union
Problem Statement	The successive Myanmar governments have used education (based on the language, culture, history and Buddhism identified with the ethnic majority Bamar) in the name of cultivating national solidarity.
Research Purpose or Questions	In 2011, the nominal civilian government initiated several reforms including education. This paper will review key relevant laws and analyze whether the legal framework allows the mother tongue-based education (MTBE) to be for all ethnic nationalities. It will also analyse the challenges for the MTBE implementation.
Literature or Theory	Interpretation and analysis are based on the premise that mother tongue-based education has 'significant cognitive and academic benefits for students' (UNESCO, 2009 & UNICEF, 2016) and 'strengthens cultural identity and heritage' (Jomtien Declaration, 1990).
Research Methods	The information will be drawn from interviews with retired and in-service teachers, relevant laws and policy, and newspapers, reports, and studies.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	This active implementation and maintenance of mother tongue based multilingual education (MTB-MLE) for all ethnic nationalities would be better suited for the country and would greatly contribute in cultivating national solidarity through recognition and respect of multiethnic identities.
Conclusion or recommendations	Guarantee of true MTB-MLE to all ethnic nationalities will greatly contribute in peace building in the country with 135 officially recognized ethnic groups.
Key Word 1	mother tongue-based education
Key Word 2	ethnic identity
Key Word 3	education
Key Word 4	multilingual
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

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Profession	Student
Title	
Name of Institution	Superior University
Country	Pakistan
Sex	
Abstract Proposal 10	
Title	Challenges in Quality of Education in HEIs of Pakistan
Problem Statement	There are various challenges in quality of education in HEIs of Pakistan that this paper will analyze.
Research Purpose or Questions	The purpose of this study is based on exploratory research to identify "Challenges in Quality of Education in HEIs of Pakistan"
Literature or Theory	"Challenges in Quality of Education in HEIs of Pakistan"
Research Methods	The research used triangulation in order to carry the reliability and validity of the data for results. So, to conduct this triangulation the researcher used questionnaire for the students, walk-in observations and interviews of the teachers.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	During the survey, Out of the 100 questionnaires 85 were returned by the respondents. Out of these 85, 7 were incorrectly filled or were left incomplete, therefore the actual sample size for this study was 78.
Conclusion or recommendations	The study concludes that there is an urgent need to reform the system of quality of education in Pakistan and for this purpose this study presents the recommendations.
Key Word 1	Curriculum
Key Word 2	Corruption
Key Word 3	Teacher's Behavior
Key Word 4	Research Work
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	11
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Title	Prof.
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Country	Taiwan
Sex	
Abstract Proposal 11	
Title	'Taiwan Among the Nations: Identity, Positionality, and Resistance in the Question for Coexistence'
Problem Statement	Taiwan (and its Christians) face an existential threat related to militarism and are seeking ways to pursue peace.
Research Purpose or Questions	How do Taiwanese Christians respond to shifting national identity and rising regional militarism?
Literature or Theory	Historical research on Taiwanese responses to conflict; recent surveys on Taiwanese Christian identity; theological reflection.
Research Methods	Historical-theological with some use of social scientific survey
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	Taiwanese identity has shifted and grown in recent years, with repercussions for Christian identity.
Conclusion or recommendations	This paper affirms the PCT's statement that "Taiwan is Taiwan" while seeking ecumenically to engage in reconciliation and restorative justice.
Key Word 1	Taiwan
Key Word 2	restorative justice
Key Word 3	positionality
Key Word 4	militarism
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	12
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Title	
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Country	THAILAND
Sex	Female
Abstract Proposal 12	
Title	Women's Roles and Contributions the Peace Process in Myanmar 2010-2020
Problem Statement	Women's participation in Myanmar peace process
Research Purpose or Questions	How have women been participating in the Myanmar Peace Process, if they are not at the peace table?
Literature or Theory	Women roles and inclusion in Myanmar Peace Process and women have managed peace process behind the table.
Research Methods	Qualitative research methodology. Primary data conduct interview for five people, three women from the grassroot and two form NGOs leader. Secondary data from relevant scholar articles, news and publications from government and non governmental institute.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	The women were participated alternative ways to exert influence on Myanmar peace process even when they have not been officially involved. Gender framework of the UN Resolution 1325 that sitting formally at the table might not work for the women in Myanmar.
Conclusion or recommendations	Women have been working and contribution to the peace process in other ways and we should recognize women informal effort for the peace process in Myanmar.
Key Word 1	Peace Process
Key Word 2	Women Participation
Key Word 3	Gender
Key Word 4	Resolution 1325
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	13
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Title	Rev.
Name of Institution	Presbyterian Church (USA)
Country	Philippines/USA
Sex	Female
Abstract Proposal 13	
Title	Jeju Truth Commissions: Peacebuilding for the Korean Peninsula
Problem Statement	Decades-long lack of political will and repression related to conflicting opinions about perpetrators and victims, diminished efforts to seek the truth related to pre-Korean War atrocities on Jeju.
Research Purpose or Questions	The purposes are to identify the pre-Korean War atrocities addressed by the Jeju 4.3 truth commission, to review the contributions of original and subsequent commissions, and to examine whether these contributions could promote peace for the Korean peninsula.
Literature or Theory	The literature that frames this research is books and published articles.
Research Methods	The method is grounded theory based on primary and secondary data.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	The expected findings include an assessment of these truth commissions that includes challenges and opportunities about promoting peace for the Korean peninsula.
Conclusion or recommendations	This paper recommends more research about the long-term impacts of these commissions on short-term and long-term peace efforts on the Korean peninsula.
Key Word 1	Korea
Key Word 2	Jeju
Key Word 3	truth commission
Key Word 4	
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	14
Profile	
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Profession	University Administration
Title	
Name of Institution	Freelance
Country	United States
Sex	Male
Abstract Proposal 14	
Title	The Role of Critical Thinking in Afghanistan Students' Education
Problem Statement	Undergoing endless armed conflict over the decades, Afghanistan experiences deep economic, political, and social problems. Afghanistan education is negligent in utilizing and teaching its culturally diverse students critical thinking in its schools. This leads schools to “rarely entail critical thinking whereby the students are more likely to draw inferences and synthesize ideas” (Kurbanov, 2016, p. 1) and are more inclined to memorize materials.
Research Purpose or Questions	This study has two purposes: (a) to examine the level of critical thinking that culturally diverse Afghanistan students experience in their K-12 learning experience that prepares them for university learning (b) to examine the barriers they may face when entering a university without the use and learning of critical thinking skills and how the introduction to this skill benefit them.
Literature or Theory	“The ultimate goal is to have students use critical thinking by identifying problems, asking questions, examining problems in context, determining the consequences for themselves and others of possible actions to solving the problems, and transform their learning – be emancipated by it – to make sound decisions in their day-to-day activities in real life” (Mimbs, 2005, p. 8).
Research Methods	This study will utilize the qualitative research methods of both the writer’s past observations while he lived and taught Afghanistan first year students at the American University of Afghanistan; and secondary research to collect data mainly in the form of text.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	It will be expected that due to the researcher’s experience and research that there have been obstacles on critical thinking and beyond now and for at least the last generation of students and since the Taliban has taken over the right to speak, the right to learn, or accepting other people will be seen to be even more accentuated (Hasona, 2021).
Conclusion or recommendations	It is recommended that Afghanistan schools place an emphasis on teaching critical thinking, what it is, and to have students think in a metacognitive, introspective way and to follow the advice of the World

	Economic Form in their Future of Jobs Report from 2018 that stated three of the top skills people will need beyond 2020 are complex problem solving, critical thinking and creativity (Centre for the New Economy and Society).
Key Word 1	Critical Thinking
Key Word 2	Afghanistan
Key Word 3	
Key Word 4	
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

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Profession	Faculty
Title	Dr.
Name of Institution	Notre Dame of Marbel University
Country	Philippines
Sex	Male
Abstract Proposal 15	
Title	THE DIALECTIC OF DECEPTION
Problem Statement	This philosophical paper contends that deception begets alienation and alienation is produced by deception, thus, we are not only exposed but very much vulnerable to some of the contemporary mechanisms of deception.
Research Purpose or Questions	How do individuals, groups, communities, institutions, nations and even the world are imploring the aid of deception in order to advance some selfish desires thus, constituting a whole sophisticated web of deceptive hypocritical world?
Literature or Theory	According to Karl Marx (1844), economic alienation causes human alienation and class conflict; and in the same way, the appropriation of the means of production causes economic alienation.
Research Methods	This philosophical paper thoroughly examines Marx's Theory of Alienation and Dialectic Materialism as they are appropriated in the various forms of deception exemplified in development models of modernity.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	Philosophy of deception is divided into two basic kinds, namely, self- and other-deception. Self-deception gave light to the most devastating kind of alienation – an alienation that is self-imposed and not just coming from human's vulnerability to deceptive systems, likewise, the other-deception also affirmed the many mechanisms of deception in the structures of development models.
Conclusion or recommendations	The dialectic of deception is a condition that needs various forms of deceptive mechanisms to cover up or at least minimize social conflict and alienating experiences of human beings.
Key Word 1	Deception
Key Word 2	Alienation
Key Word 3	Dialectic Materialism
Key Word 4	Dialectic of Deception
Key Word 5	Development Models

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	16
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Profession	Faculty
Title	Dr.
Name of Institution	University of Kerala
Country	India
Sex	
Abstract Proposal 16	
Title	Religious Institutions: Inevitable Parts of the Peacebuilding in the Middle East
Problem Statement	Peacebuilding of the United Nations in the Middle East is dominated by the secular framework despite the clear evidence of increasing role of religion in legitimizing conflict and conflict resolution.
Research Purpose or Questions	The proposed paper explores how the religious institutions can get legitimacy and moral superiority in the peacebuilding when the official states institutions failed to get them.
Literature or Theory	Recently, many studies have challenged the secularization theory and stereotype against religion as a source of violence.
Research Methods	It will take case study of Israel-Palestine conflict and will analyze the potential role of religious institutions in the peacebuilding
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	Religious institutions enjoy moral superiority and legitimacy in the society compared to state leaders. So, their support is useful for getting mass-legitimacy for any peacebuilding in the region
Conclusion or recommendations	Religious leaders and institutions should be involved in the peacebuilding and resolving conflicts like Israel-Palestine conflicts
Key Word 1	Middle East
Key Word 2	Conflict resolution
Key Word 3	Israel
Key Word 4	Palestine
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	17
Profile	
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Profession	Retired
Title	Prof.
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Country	United States
Sex	Male
Abstract Proposal 17	
Title	Educating for Peace in the 21 st Century: Are We Failing?
Problem Statement	Are we failing to educate today's student in ways that foster civility, tolerance and peace?
Research Purpose or Questions	What can higher education do to ensure that students are equipped to deal with wicked problems and facilitate discourse that is civil and tolerates different views.
Literature or Theory	University students, age 18-24, are developing adults who benefit from learning activities that facilitate personal traits such as tolerance, civility and empathy.
Research Methods	Literature and discourse on today changing world
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	Higher education was failed to provide necessary whole person education to help ensure that the populous and leadership are equipped to deal with the wicked problems facing humanity.
Conclusion or recommendations	We need to reevaluate higher education roles in fostering peace.
Key Word 1	Higher Education
Key Word 2	21st Century Education
Key Word 3	Civility
Key Word 4	
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

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Profile	
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Profession	Student
Title	
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Country	United States of America
Sex	Male
Abstract Proposal 18	
Title	Peace through culture and religion, lessons from Morocco
Problem Statement	Culture and religion in the peace equation, Lessons from Morocco
Research Purpose or Questions	Conflicts are defined as the product of a cultural or religious clash, but from a different point of view, to what extent can culture and religion contribute to peace?
Literature or Theory	Democratic peace theory
Research Methods	Dividers and Connectors Analysis
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	Culture and religion are at the same time dividers and connectors as understood from the Moroccan experience of peace with Jewish community
Conclusion or recommendations	The equation of peace or conflict changes with the change in our view of paradigms. If we look at the difference of culture as a threat, it will generate conflict and violence, but if we look at it as wealth, this inevitably leads to peace and coexistence.
Key Word 1	Religion
Key Word 2	Culture
Key Word 3	Morocco
Key Word 4	Jewish
Key Word 5	Peace

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	19
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Sex	
Abstract Proposal 19	
Title	PEACEBUILDING THROUGH VALUE-BASED PEACE EDUCATION IN UNIVERSITIES
Problem Statement	The purpose of this study is to: analyze the contribution of the concept of peace education and values in building community peace efforts to make peace, so far, still need serious treatment in the face of the increasingly diverse world community. By building peaceful education that empowers basic values in higher education, it will further strengthen the building of peace in the world community
Research Purpose or Questions	- (Note: blank; answered with a dash mark "-")
Literature or Theory	Peace education, values, and character for peace education in college
Research Methods	This research method uses a literature review, with the data sources being theories, research results, and other document sources whose results are analyzed by content analysis techniques.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	The results of this study indicate that student character can be formed through character education based on peace education and the core values of higher education
Conclusion or recommendations	Building the character of superior students can be done through character education based on peace education and college core values
Key Word 1	character education
Key Word 2	peace education
Key Word 3	core values
Key Word 4	
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	20
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Name of Institution	Retired
Country	
Sex	
Abstract Proposal 20	
Title	Peace and Development Issues of the T’boli People in Southern Mindanao
Problem Statement	This paper sought to discover the peace and development issues of the T’boli tribe, their responses to these issues, their problems met as they addressed these issues and the theories or classifications which can possibly be drawn from their responses to these problems.
Research Purpose or Questions	People in Mindanao have long been dreaming of peace as the region has been laden with so much poverty, cultural divide, massive ecological degradation, armed clashes and displacement, despite peace talks with government and interventions of non-government organizations.
Literature or Theory	The researcher classified the responses of the T’boli according to their perception of the four main issues appropriated from the Peace Framework according to Toh Swee Hin & Cawagas (1986) namely: cultural disintegration, structural violence, militarization and environmental degradation.
Research Methods	In this Qualitative Exploratory research, the writer conducted an ethnographic fieldwork, Focused Group Discussion, interview and also used secondary literature to answer the problem.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	The T’boli people can be classified into: First, those who engage the state to meet their needs; Second, those who collaborate with the state as they critically analyze T’boli issues as arising from policies that are set in order to accommodate political and economic structures; Third, those who merely exist, who unaware of or are indifferent by issues around them.
Conclusion or recommendations	Despite the T’boli’s glorious past of living peacefully, communally, sustainably and in harmony with nature, they are now beset with voluminous policies and structures which they no longer recognize to be either protective of or detrimental to their destiny as a tribe.
Key Word 1	T’boli
Key Word 2	Mindanao
Key Word 3	Peace Issues
Key Word 4	
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	21
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Sex	
Abstract Proposal 21	
Title	Cyber Crime: Shaping the perception post covid'19 with respect to the Indian Cyber Laws
Problem Statement	This paper investigates the problem of cyber-crime and India and how to shape the perception post covid-19 with respect to the Indian Cyber Laws
Research Purpose or Questions	a. What are the prominent reasons for the increase in the rate of cyber-crimes over the years? b. Impact of the covid-19 pandemic on cyber-crime? c. What are the preventive laws related to cyber-crime existing in India?
Literature or Theory	Some literature used include: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Gupta and Kumar, 2019). With the help of the research, the author has tried to spread awareness about sex extortion through online sites. 2. (Bawa D. & Marwah D., 2011). Both the authors of this paper have tried to explain cyberethics from different aspects. 3. (Ken T., 2010). The author has given the emphasis on the matter of teaching pre-adults about the internet, he has focused upon the issue of cyber-bullying and impacts of atmosphere or climate due to online behavior.
Research Methods	The research is being designed for making a qualitative investigation about the reasons for the increase in cases against different types of cyber-crimes and discussion upon the cyber laws available in the Indian law system. The "Analytical Method" will be employed.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	Cyber Crime is of various types like web-based application attacks, SQL injections, Cross-site scripting, AI-powered attacks, Spear phishing attacks, and many others. Covid-19 pandemic had increased the crime rates of cyber-crime. There has been a great rise in cyber-crime rates which can be noted due to many sets of reasons like easy access system, storing confidential data in a small space altogether, gaps in coding due to complex mechanisms, careless attitude towards our own devices and their security.

Conclusion or recommendations	Cyber-crime can be prevented by using strong passwords, using VPN, preserving confidential information, privately managing social media sites, keeping confidential data in zipped files, etc. In India, several cyber laws are available, either in the IT Act of 2000 or some are provided in the Indian Penal Code, 1886.
Key Word 1	Covid-19
Key Word 2	Cyber-crime
Key Word 3	Cyber-laws
Key Word 4	Cyber-security
Key Word 5	Hacking

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	22
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Abstract Proposal 22	
Title	Cold War 2.0 and The Ukraine Crisis: Causes, Effects, and Tasks Ahead
Problem Statement	We are faced with the problem of getting only one narrative about the Ukraine Crisis from mainstream media (MSM).
Research Purpose or Questions	To present contending perspectives about the causes, effects, and what needs to be done
Literature or Theory	This paper used the historical, critical, hermeneutic, and nomological approaches, as well as espousing a peace studies positionality.
Research Methods	This paper focused on the Ukraine crisis as a case study using a qualitative research design. Qualitative data are collected from different media which are coded to yield different narratives of the same case in point.
Findings (for completed research)	NATO, Ukraine, and Russia have three different perspectives about the conflict, its causes, consequences, and what is to be done.
Conclusion or recommendation	Peace scholars and activists call for an alternative path for peace, not escalation of the war from all sides.
Key Word 1	Ukraine crisis
Key Word 2	NATO
Key Word 3	Peace studies
Key Word 4	Russia
Key Word 5	War

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

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Country	Thailand
Sex	Male
Abstract Proposal 23	
Title	How are the different? Thai university teachers describe Chinese students
Problem Statement	Chinese students bring to the Thai classroom expectations for student-faculty interactions, classroom behavior, class assignments, and other assumptions than do Thai students.
Research Purpose or Questions	How is teaching Chinese students different from teaching Thai university students?
Literature or Theory	Sociology of education
Research Methods	We are using Auto-Ethnography, reflecting on the relative experiences of the authors (and colleagues) teaching Chinese university students at Payap University, Chiangmai.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	Chinese students have different habits and ways of looking at university life than do Thai students.
Conclusion or recommendations	University administrators developing programs for Chinese students in Thailand need to pay closer attention to the assumptions Chinese students bring to the university classroom.
Key Word 1	Thai higher education
Key Word 2	International Education
Key Word 3	
Key Word 4	
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	24
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Country	Thailand
Sex	Female
Abstract Proposal 24	
Title	Addressing the State of Absolute Monarchy to Attain Democracy in Eswatini
Problem Statement	Over decades, the kingdom of Eswatini have experienced continuous and persistent democracy activism that has caused heightened tension to citizens resulting in several incidents of violence, all of which posed a serious threat to peace.
Research Purpose or Questions	This paper will answer the following threefold questions: What is the state of absolute monarchy in Eswatini? Can non- violent resistance be used as a peace building effort mechanism to oppose the problem of absolute monarchy to attain democracy in Eswatini? And what are the suggestions to curb with the occurring problem of opposing absolute monarchy to attain democracy in Eswatini?
Literature or Theory	The literature review will be into two sections, opposing the state of absolute monarchy and different philosopher’s view on non-violent resistance respectively.
Research Methods	Grounded theory based on secondary data while tools to be used are published journals, articles, news and reports. This study will use qualitative technique approach as findings are expected to be analyzed Manually
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	The expected findings will include the state of absolute monarchy, whether non-violent resistance can be used to attain democracy and suggestions to the problem.
Conclusion or recommendations	This paper recommends that future research scholars should explore this problem engaging peace building attributes such as conflict transformation, prevention, and peace making.
Key Word 1	Absolute Monarchy
Key Word 2	Democracy
Key Word 3	Non-violent resistance
Key Word 4	Eswatini
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	25
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Sex	Female
Abstract Proposal 25	
Title	THE IMPLEMENTATION OF COMPREHENSIVE DEVELOPMENT AGENDA- EXECUTIVE LEGISLATIVE AGENDA (CDP-ELA) IN SELECTED MUNICIPALITIES OF MAGUINDANAO PROVINCE IN THE PHILIPPINES
Problem Statement	The problems encountered in the implementation of CDP-ELA were identified.
Research Purpose or Questions	This study aimed to assess the extent of implementation of Comprehensive Development Plan – Executive Legislative Agenda of selected municipalities of Maguindanao Province in the Philippines.
Literature or Theory	The concept of public policy is used in this study to analyze the implementation of Executive-Legislative Agenda in selected municipalities of Maguindanao.
Research Methods	This study used the descriptive- evaluative research design and total enumeration.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	Some challenges encountered in the implementation of CDP-ELA are unstable peace and order, lack of budget, lack of time, lack of support and lack of political will.
Conclusion or recommendations	The extent of the implementation of the major projects contained in CDP-ELA varies from one municipality to the other.
Key Word 1	public policy
Key Word 2	peace and order
Key Word 3	project implementation
Key Word 4	Mindanao
Key Word 5	Philippines

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	26
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Abstract Proposal 26	
Title	Interfaith Dialogue for Peacebuilding: promoting religious unity in Myanmar
Problem Statement	This paper addresses the problem of the conflicts in Myanmar among religious minorities and the majority Buddhism in 2012 to 2017, resulted in irreversible damages.
Research Purpose or Questions	To find out if interfaith dialogue initiatives in Myanmar promote unity among religion and strengthen peacebuilding. This paper explored and analyzed interfaith dialogues initiatives by the types and contents and the challenges encountered
Literature or Theory	The study is built on the concept of Merdjanova, and Brodeur (2009) perceiving interfaith dialogue as an initiative that involves different groups, levels and forms, and dealing with issues crucial for transformative and sustainable peace
Research Methods	The study was done through review of literature, reports and documents, case study and interview.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	The research found out various initiatives in Myanmar ranging from the Government to INGOs and local organizations, the forms of interfaith dialogue used, the contents discussed and the challenges faced and their achievements.
Conclusion or recommendations	The fragmented efforts moderately strengthen the unity of religions, however, the commitment of the Government and its constant leadership is required to synergize the efforts for a long term cohesion of religions and peacebuilding in Myanmar
Key Word 1	Interfaith Dialogue
Key Word 2	Peacebuilding
Key Word 3	Religious Unity
Key Word 4	
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

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Abstract Proposal 27	
Problem Statement	Muslim, Christian, and Indigenous Discourses on the Peace Framework Agreement in Mindanao, Philippines
Research Purpose or Questions	This paper deals with the problem that confronts the Muslims, the Christians, and the Indigenous Communities (tri-people) in Mindanao Philippines.
Literature or Theory	articles, government public documents, annual reports of the NGOs, that reveal the discourses of the tri-people in their peace agreement with one another for the analysis of this study.
Research Methods	Qualitative content analysis through Grounded theory is applied as a method for the analysis of the documents or discourses as collected data.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	The struggle for self-determination is one of the root causes of conflicts and each group has its own discourses on its standing on the peace process. The inclusive tri-people rationality is the proposed framework for a peace agreement in Mindanao.
Conclusion or recommendations	The rationality of tri-people on inclusivity and transparency must be the focus of the peace agenda of the Philippine government because the discourses involve all parties on power-sharing as mechanisms for peace.

	The paper recommends further research on cultural and ethnic studies specifically on identity-based violence between ethnic groups.
Key Word 1	tri-people
Key Word 2	peace framework agreement
Key Word 3	Mindanao, Philippines
Key Word 4	
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	28
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Abstract Proposal 28	
Title	Peacebuilding in the digital age
Problem Statement	Digital technologies have changed almost all life scenes; thus, this transformation has influenced the peacebuilding field.
Research Purpose or Questions	The questions this paper attempts to answer are: 1) How do digital technologies transform the field of peacebuilding in Korean civil society? 2) How is this transformation different for different societies, and why?
Literature or Theory	Digital Peacebuilding and PeaceTech
Research Methods	The method used is an inductive approach for qualitative research based on literature reviews and secondary data.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	The expected findings are the transformation of civil organizations' activities over the past 30 years in Korea according to the development of digital technologies, and the differences of the same technology which is used for different purposes depending on the conflict area and the general area.
Conclusion or recommendations	This paper concludes that various challenges arising in the digital societies can be solved through 'digital mediation' just as the role of mediators is significant for conflict transformation.
Key Word 1	digital technology
Key Word 2	transformation
Key Word 3	civil society
Key Word 4	peacebuilding
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	29
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Country	India
Sex	Male
Abstract Proposal 29	
Title	Seeking the significance of effective leadership in upbringing communities
Problem Statement	Leadership is all about being with pragmatic towards every situation but management is a question of position
Research Purpose or Questions	This paper attempts to find out the correlation between effective leadership and community development
Literature or Theory	Theory of transformational Leadership
Research Methods	Subject to primary and secondary sources with a special concern to data analytics and development reports
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	Leaders of every communities and nation should be farsighted and ethically well-packed. They have the resposility to keep themselves unbiased and uncorrupted.
Conclusion or recommendations	The greatest success of every celebrated leaders lies in building a sustainable next generation of awesome leaders.
Key Word 1	Leadership
Key Word 2	Community Development
Key Word 3	Progressive Society
Key Word 4	Ethics
Key Word 5	Leadership Qualities

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	30
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Sex	
Abstract Proposal 30	
Title	Imagining God in the Lockdown
Problem Statement	If ways of imagining God is influenced, shaped, and informed by concrete historical conditions, then new images of God can emerge around the experiences of lockdowns.
Research Purpose or Questions	In this research I aim to understand how Filipinos imagine God during state-imposed lockdown due to COVID-19 pandemic. The novelty of experiences in the lockdown demands scrutiny and elucidation.
Literature or Theory	Grounded Theory, Political theologies of Agamben and Schmitt
Research Methods	Through content analysis of statements, sermons, speeches of government and ecumenical leaders and transcribed texts of focus group discussions I organized into categories the metaphors and phrases depicting God.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	This study shows that in the context of lockdown, the transcendent images of God are utilized to cover the state's disorganized and poor response to the pandemic. The immanent images of God correspond to the church and ecumenical organizations eclectic mobilization of its resources to the crises that resulted to people's depiction of them as God here on earth.
Conclusion or recommendations	In democracies like the Philippines, the churches on the ground are places to exercises people's subjectivities.
Key Word 1	pandemic
Key Word 2	Political theology
Key Word 3	grounded theory
Key Word 4	Covid
Key Word 5	Philippines

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	31
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Sex	
Abstract Proposal 31	
Title	The Impact of Hatred and Siblinghood Meta-Narratives in Ambonese Inter-Religious Relationship
Problem Statement	The two contradicted meta-narratives (hatred and sibling-hood) are both exist and contribute in the Ambonese People's ideas about "the others".
Research Purpose or Questions	This research aims to show the impact of the two contradictory meta-narratives about the "other" after the Ambon ethno-religious riot in 1999-2006, by analyzing how those contradicted meta-narrative play a significant role in the construction of idea about "the others".
Literature or Theory	this research used two main concepts, namely: the master-narrative theory by Halverson et al and the construction of belief theory by Bar-Tal.
Research Methods	this research used an ethnographic research method.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	Those two contradicted meta-narratives (hatred and sibling-hood) are equally preserved and simultaneously become the basis for the people to understand the reality of diversity around them. interestingly, the idea about the other as a product of those two contradicted meta-narratives also have a significant impact in the process of post-conflict reconciliation in nowadays Ambon
Conclusion or recommendations	those contradicted meta-narratives eventually produces an obstacle for the Ambonese people to create an inclusive interaction space based on their shared value and narrative, but not oblivious to the differences.
Key Word 1	Meta-narratives
Key Word 2	Christian
Key Word 3	Muslim
Key Word 4	Relationship
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	32
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Country	
Sex	
Abstract Proposal 32	
Title	Co-Coloniality, Multiple Coloniality, and Successive Coloniality: Discerning the Levels and Orientations of Reconciliation Needed in Taiwan
Problem Statement	The scope of the transitional justice in Taiwan is limited by the legal periodisation (1945-1992), preventing the full reconciliation in Taiwan to be conceived, and confining the implication of the project to domestic politics.
Research Purpose or Questions	The paper seeks to identify the wider implication of Taiwan's transitional justice.
Literature or Theory	The concepts of co-coloniality, multiple coloniality, and successive coloniality the papaer invokes are proposed by historian (Andrade 2013) and political philosopher (Wu 2016).
Research Methods	The paper applies a systemic contextualisation of the multi-layered construction of Taiwanese identity through the concepts of co-coloniality, multiple coloniality, and successive coloniality.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	With the centrality of colonial experiences in Taiwan's transitional justice, Taiwan's case shares more similarities with some cases (countries having experienced colonialism, e.g., India etc.), and the decolonial perspective should be applied to the similarities Taiwan finds with some other cases (countries having experienced dictatorial rule, e.g., East Germany etc.).
Conclusion or recommendations	The Church in Taiwan should apply a dialogical approach with first, different groups experiencing different colonialities, second, different religions in Taiwan, and lastly, with anti-colonial denominations in both the West and the Rest.
Key Word 1	Transitional justice
Key Word 2	Coloniality
Key Word 3	Taiwan
Key Word 4	dialogical decolonisation
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	33
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Abstract Proposal 33	
Title	Jesus' Kingdom of God as a New Paradigm for Peace
Problem Statement	Jesus' vision for peace for his society within first-century Palestine remains largely unclear within modern scholarship.
Research Purpose or Questions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How was peace understood in first-century Judaism? 2. How did Jesus' teaching on God's Kingdom relate to his idea of peace? 3. How is Jesus' Kingdom of God motif a new paradigm for peace?
Literature or Theory	History of Judaism and First-Century Palestine, historical Jesus research.
Research Methods	Literature review, conceptual reflection.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	The paper will attempt to show that Jesus had a strategy for peace for his own society within first-century Palestine that was constructed upon the Kingdom of God leitmotif.
Conclusion or recommendations	I believe Jesus' strategy can contribute to contemporary peace theory and practice.
Key Word 1	First-Century Palestine
Key Word 2	Kingdom of God
Key Word 3	
Key Word 4	
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

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Country	Philippines
Sex	Female
Abstract Proposal 34	
Title	The Effects of Public Service Excellence, Ethics & Accountability Program in Selected Municipalities of Maguindanao in the Philippines
Problem Statement	This paper aimed to determine whether or not the Public Service Excellence, Ethics and Accountability Program have contributed to the improvement of the service delivery of the recipients Local Government Units in Maguindanao, Philippines.
Research Purpose or Questions	The study aimed to determine if there is or there is no significant improvement to the service delivery of Local Government Units recipients after the implementation of the program in terms of office environment, office personnel, office procedure accountability and transparency.
Literature or Theory	The study used the concept of good governance and Batho Pele Principles.
Research Methods	This study is both qualitative and quantitative in nature.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	The program has significant effects to the improvement of service delivery.
Conclusion or recommendations	There shall be continuity of the program in other municipalities.
Key Word 1	governance
Key Word 2	accountability
Key Word 3	ethics
Key Word 4	
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	35
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Title	
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Abstract Proposal 35	
Title	Dap-ay: Traditional Liturgical Center of Igorot People
Problem Statement	The study aims to look into the experiences of Episcopal clergy in Cordillera in relation to dap-ay as a traditional liturgical center.
Research Purpose or Questions	What are the concepts of dap-ay that can be reflected in the Episcopal Church liturgy?
Literature or Theory	The Behaviorist Theory which is founded by J.B Watson, supports Dap-ay being a liturgical center of a community.
Research Methods	The process involves the qualitative research design specifically the use of phenomenological approach through interview, analysis and interpretation of the data.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	This research sheds light on the similarities in the conduct of rituals in the Dap-ay and rites in the Christian altar.
Conclusion or recommendations	Based on the expected findings, ecclesiastical resolutions can be made better as to the inculcation of cultural practices into worship.
Key Word 1	Dap-ay
Key Word 2	Igorot indigenous people in the Cordilleras in the northern Philippines
Key Word 3	liturgy
Key Word 4	tradition
Key Word 5	worship

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

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Abstract Proposal 36	
Title	Bangkok Catholic Views on the Buddhist Concepts of Karma and Reincarnation
Problem Statement	How Thailand's miniscule Christian minority live their faith lives and/or adjust their belief system in an overwhelmingly Buddhist environment.
Research Purpose or Questions	Do Thai Catholics believe in the Buddhist concepts of karma and reincarnation?
Literature or Theory	"Theological Correctness": How far is a tiny religious minority willing to assimilate religious concepts of the majority.
Research Methods	The qualitative research uses the semi-structured interview with snowball sampling method.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	Bangkok Catholics have mostly assimilated the Buddhist concept of "karma," as it has an equivalent in Christian teaching, but not reincarnation.
Conclusion or recommendations	There can be central tenets of faith but religion is always local in the ways they are lived out.
Key Word 1	Thailand
Key Word 2	Catholic
Key Word 3	karma
Key Word 4	reincarnation
Key Word 5	Theological Correctness

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

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Sex	Male
Abstract Proposal 37	
Title	Interpretations of International Peacebuilding by local groups in conflict in Africa: the role played by the perception of Horror
Problem Statement	International peacebuilding failed in bringing lasting peace in African fragile states in conflicts
Research Purpose or Questions	Why do international peacebuilding fail in Africa?
Literature or Theory	Symbolic interactionism
Research Methods	Capacity and potentiatiy of creating territorial instability by local groups in conflicts in Africa gives them possibility to integrate and control political structures. That lead to the failure of international peacebuilding
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	Capacity and potentiatiy of creating territorial instability by local groups in conflicts in Africa give's them possibility to integrate and control political structures. That lead to the failure of international peacebuilding
Conclusion or recommendations	Peacebuilders may stop integrating civilians armed groups into political structures
Key Word 1	Peacebuilding
Key Word 2	Perception of Horror
Key Word 3	Bargaining power
Key Word 4	Civil armed groups
Key Word 5	Power sharing

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

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Sex	Female
Abstract Proposal 38	
Title	The Ethics of Reconciliation
Problem Statement	the problematic nature of the ethics of reconciliation or peacebuilding as a process
Research Purpose or Questions	three questions: what the ethics of reconciliation means; why the ethics of reconciliation are significant to deeply divided societies; and how it works
Literature or Theory	descriptive and applied ethics
Research Methods	literature review
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	the ethical questions
Conclusion or recommendations	scholars and practitioners in the field of peacebuilding develop ethics of reconciliation according to the traditional contexts
Key Word 1	ethics of reconciliation
Key Word 2	protracted conflict
Key Word 3	deeply divided societies
Key Word 4	
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	39
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Abstract Proposal 39	
Title	Awareness and Application of the Principles and Rules on Warfare: The Case of the Moro Islamic Liberation Front (MILF) in Balindong, Lanao del Sur
Problem Statement	Despite awareness to the principles and rules on warfare, Balindong-based Moro Islamic Liberation Front violates some of these principles and rules during actual combat operations.
Research Purpose or Questions	This research aims to determine the awareness of Balindong-based Moro Islamic Liberation Front members on the principles and rules on warfare and which of these are observed or violated during armed confrontations.
Literature or Theory	This study utilizes the principles of International Humanitarian Law, the four Geneva Conventions in 1949 and their Additional Protocols in 1977 and 2005, and other international treaties and local laws in identifying the principles and rules on warfare taught during Moro Islamic Liberation Front training sessions and their observance or violation during combat operations.
Research Methods	This research embodies a qualitative-exploratory-descriptive type employing survey and interview methods in gathering data.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	Based on the gathered data, the findings include the following: (1) awareness to the principles and rules on warfare was spearheaded by Moro Islamic Liberation Front commanders and other local ustadj or ustadja utilizing the Holy Qur'an, Hadith, and their own documents; (2) the Moro Islamic Liberation Front members observe the principles of distinction and superfluous injury or unnecessary suffering based on Islamic reasons and the right of the civilians to live, while they violate the principle of chivalry and the age requirement for combatants, with the utilization of ambushes and participation of children, aged 10 to 15, as combatants in the organization; and (3) the narratives of Moro Islamic Liberation Front commanders and leaders proved that the principles of military necessity, distinction, and humanity were observed with the employment of weapons indispensable to the objectives of war, protecting civilians, and treating combatants humanely, while they violate the principles of chivalry and superfluous injury or unnecessary suffering

	were violated with the utilization of ambushes and bombs during armed confrontation.
Conclusion or recommendations	While the implementation of the principles and rules on warfare is difficult during armed confrontations, a lasting peace is very possible in the Philippines if all major stakeholders, such as the Government, the Moro Islamic Liberation Front, and civil society groups, work together for the common good of the whole Filipino citizenry, especially the marginalized Muslim communities in Mindanao.
Key Word 1	International Law
Key Word 2	International Humanitarian Law
Key Word 3	Religion (Islam)
Key Word 4	Peace building
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	40
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Abstract Proposal 40	
Title	Weaving Suffering to Heal Trauma: A Case Study of Timorese Weaver's Pilgrimage from a Victim to a Survivor of Domestic Violence and Human Trafficking
Problem Statement	Women are living in patriarchal society that placed them to subordinate than men, vulnerable to be violated and exploited physically, mentally, and sexually in domestic and public area. Indonesia National Commission on Violence against Women recorded since 2010 to 2020 there were 2.775.042 gender-based violence. In 2021 only 5.700 cases reported in the commission. The Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection stated in 2011-2013 stated that 55,36 percent from 509 trafficking in person cases were women. Specifically, in East Nusa Tenggara Province (NTT) domestic violence and human trafficking are closed related to women as its victims which is remained such an endless suffering and trauma in silence.
Research Purpose or Questions	In the pilgrimage, how does the woman weave her suffering and trauma to be a survivor in patriarchal society?
Literature or Theory	Aruna Gnanadason, Musimbi Kanyoro, and Lucia Ann McSpadden, "Women, Violence, and Nonviolent Change," WCC, 1996; Karen Campbell-Nelson (ed), "Tuhan tak Berdagang- Perdagangan Orang, Trauma, dan Teologi di Nusa Tenggara Timur," BPK Gunung Mulia, 2020.
Research Methods	Participatory action research.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	Found woman's power in dealing with her suffering and trauma in her pilgrimage that strengthen her to be a survivor in patriarchal society.
Conclusion or recommendations	Readers will be taking part in the woman's pilgrimage as a sign of solidarity.
Key Word 1	Pilgrimage
Key Word 2	Victim
Key Word 3	Survivor
Key Word 4	Human Trafficking
Key Word 5	Domestic Violence

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	41
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Abstract Proposal 41	
Title	Analysis of the Cognitive Consciousness on Yonisomanasikâra
Problem Statement	Human suffer/experience depression due to the feeling of guilt over having made mistakes because of ignorance or negligence but the ego does not allow itself to admit its mistakes, resulting the mental health problems.
Research Purpose or Questions	This study will examine the relationship between Yonisomanasikâra and ego which is vital for the better understanding of the thought process thus improve the mental health.
Literature or Theory	Literature study on analysis of Cognitive process from Abhidhammatthasangaha and relationship between Manasikâra which is “attention” or “ego-centric demanding” and Yonisomanasikâra which is “attention rooted in reality”.
Research Methods	For this paper, I will use first person approach study according to Abhidhamma teaching and focusing on analysis of details on Cognitive Consciousness by practicing comprehensive vipassana meditation.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	Even though Yonisomanasikâra is inner qualities or perfection that may not be instantaneous but to build up over a period of time, expected finding on cognitive ability of achieving right or wise attention which will contribute improvement for mental health.
Conclusion or recommendations	Recommendation further study of analysis in both long-term or short-term meditation practitioners by qualitative and quantitative research approach.
Key Word 1	Cognitive Consciousness
Key Word 2	Yonisomanasikâra
Key Word 3	
Key Word 4	
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	42
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Abstract Proposal 42	
Title	Communal Tension and Social Cohesion in India: Pathways for Positive Praxis.
Problem Statement	The rise of communal tension in India in the backdrop of religious fascism.
Research Purpose or Questions	To investigate the possibilities of inter-disciplinary action and policy practice in ensuring social cohesion and national unity.
Literature or Theory	Durkheimian group level property of collective efferevescence examined under the light of the idea of 'imagined communities' by Benedict Anderson.
Research Methods	A systematic review of literature directed by the analysis of the events of communal tension in India.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	The research identifies the importance of historical narrative, equitable economic development, and shared religious practice in ensuring religious plurality and communal cohesion.
Conclusion or recommendations	The possibilities that can be unfurled as Indians of diverse religio-cultural backgrounds come together under the spirit of anti-colonial struggle and nation building.
Key Word 1	Social Cohesion
Key Word 2	Social Policy
Key Word 3	Communal Tension
Key Word 4	
Key Word 5	

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

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Abstract Proposal 43	
Title	Disarmament of Private Citizens in Lanao del Sur for Sustainable Peacebuilding
Problem Statement	Programs on disarming private citizens are centred on economic incentives, undermining the culture, historicity, and security as important factors for the proliferation in the region.
Research Purpose or Questions	How can loose firearms in Lanao del Sur be effectively managed and reduced?
Literature or Theory	Government and non-governmental organizations have failed to understand proliferation of loose firearms in Lanao del Sur
Research Methods	Review of existing literature
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	The research will address how to effectively manage and reduce the firearms in Lanao del Sur which post a major threat to the “normalization period” as Bangsamoro Autonomous Region Muslim Mindanao (BARMM) undergoes its transition from conflict to post-conflict.
Conclusion or recommendations	For effective disarmament of private citizens or civilians: culture and tradition vis-à-vis historicity are major influences on the domestic proliferation of loose firearms, aside from a lack of security
Key Word 1	Culture of violence or culture of resistance
Key Word 2	Small arms and light weapons
Key Word 3	Bangsamoro
Key Word 4	Normalization
Key Word 5	Peacebuilding

Abstract Proposals for the First Annual International Conference

Reference Number	44
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Abstract Proposal 44	
Title	Islam, Political Violence and Search for Peace
Problem Statement	Daily violence and conflicts reported in various forms of media across the world relates their connection, mostly, to Islam and its adherents. Muslim diaspora in the United States and Europe are often clubbed together with Islamists involving in political violence elsewhere, thereby producing a host of alienated Muslims.
Research Purpose or Questions	The paper argues that such peace is achievable through strong networks of inter-faith dialogue, deeper understanding of Islam, and emphasizing more on inquiring upon institutional histories and shared experiences of community building efforts. It also seeks to critically investigate if de-secularization and de-privatization of Islam in many Muslim and non-Muslim countries is heading toward harmonization of religious and cultural differences thereby avoiding frictions with other non-Muslim communities.
Literature or Theory	Peace here is taken as not merely an absence of violence but the achievement of structural, cultural and direct peace as explained by Johan Galtung
Research Methods	Historical Institutional understanding of the subject.
Findings (for completed research) or expected findings (for research in progress)	The de-secularization and de-privatization of Islam in many Muslim and non-Muslim countries is heading toward harmonization of religious and cultural differences thereby avoiding frictions with other non-Muslim communities.
Conclusion or recommendations	If de-secularization of Islam is heading toward harmonization of religious and cultural differences, the pertinent question is whether this would result in inter-faith peace and harmony.
Key Word 1	Modernity
Key Word 2	Media
Key Word 3	Islam
Key Word 4	Christianity
Key Word 5	

